

Energy System Modelling Using OSeMOSYS

Assignment 1: General Questions

1.1. Introduction to Fossil Power Plants

1. Which of these is an example of a fossil power plant?
 - a. Hydropower plant
 - b. Coal power plant
 - c. Geothermal power plant
 - d. Solar power plant

2. What does the concept of 'Energy Transition' refer to?
 - a. Increased use of fossil fuels in energy systems
 - b. Converting one form of energy to another
 - c. Transformation of the energy sector to use more low-carbon and renewable energy sources
 - d. Development of off-grid solutions for electricity demand

1.2. Fossil Power Plants in OSeMOSYS

3. Let's consider that the efficiency of the natural gas power plant is equal to 40%. If you set the Output Activity Ratio equal to 1, what is the value of the Input Activity Ratio for this technology? Round your answer to the nearest hundredth. Do not use units in your answer; write only the plain number.

4. In OSeMOSYS, which cost parameter is used to consider the one-time costs of building a power plant?
 - a. Variable Cost
 - b. Capital Cost
 - c. Fixed Cost
 - d. Operational Cost

1.3. Impacts of Fossil Power Plants

5. Which of the following best describes oil and gas prices?
 - a. Variable over time due to changes in supply and/or demand
 - b. Constant over time

- c. Randomly varying over time
 - d. Variable over time due to geopolitical issues
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- 6. What is an example impact of the coal supply chain?
 - a. Carbon dioxide emissions
 - b. Degradation of aquatic habitats
 - c. Loss of wildlife habitats
 - d. Both of the above

1.4. Transmission and Distribution

- 7. Let's consider an electricity demand equal to 640 PJ. The distribution system has an efficiency of 95%, while the transmission system incurs losses equivalent to 7%. Based on this information, what should the electricity generation be? Round your answer to the nearest hundredth. Do not use units in your answer; write only the plain number.

- 8. What is the generic code name for Power Transmission in OSeMOSYS?
 - a. ELCTRN
 - b. PWRTRN
 - c. PWRDIST
 - d. PWRCOA